

GREENHOUSE GASES EMISSIONS AND ANIMAL HUSBANDRY SECTOR. GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

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Abstract

Increased concentrations of CH₄ (methane), CO₂ (carbon dioxide) și N₂O (nitrous oxide), known as greenhouse gases (GHG) with major implications in climate change phenomenon, are raising serious environmental concerns. Animal husbandry sector has developed significantly over the last decades in order to meet the growing needs of the population when it comes to meat consumption. This fact implicitly translates into the generation of much higher concentrations of pollutants that are being released into the air. The scientific literature highlights that there is a link between the livestock sector (bovine, sheep, pigs and poultry) and GHG emissions, sector which is globally responsible for 18% of total anthropogenic GHG emissions. The paper makes a radiography and a synthesis of scientific data and information on the current state of the art of research regarding the implications and contribution of animal husbandry/livestock sector in the generation of GHG, while proposing mitigation methods in order to counteract the negative effects. The research methodology consisted in screening the specific academic references regarding the approached research topic, followed by the selection and the review of the most significant ones. The results confirm the central hypothesis that the livestock sector, animal husbandry in this case, is an important source of greenhouse gases, being mandatory to adopt strict management measures aimed at keeping these emissions under control.

Keywords: *Greenhouse gases; animal husbandry sector; emissions; CH₄; N₂O; CO₂; mitigation methods.*

INTRODUCTION

Earth's global mean surface temperature has increased from the end of the XIXth century, each of the last three decades being warmer than the previous ones (Stocker et al., 2013, cited in Chang et al., 2017). If the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions continue to increase without adopting mitigation measures, the surface's temperature will be higher and higher during the XXIst century (Chang et al., 2017). The continuous warming phenomenon is predicted through the World Climate Research Program, respectively through the Climate Model Intercomparison Project CMIP3 and Climate Model Intercomparison Project CMIP3 (Meehl et al., 2007; Taylor, Stoufer and Meehl, 2012 cited in Chang et al., 2017). Europe has warmed more than the global mean (terrestrial and oceanic) since the pre-industrial period and it is envisioned to warm quicker than it in the XXIst century. According to the models and forecast projections of different climatic scenarios, Europe's annual mean temperature, for the period 2071–2100 would be with 1–5.5°C higher than for the period 1971–2000 (Chang et al., 2017). In this context, in 2015, during the Paris Climate Conference, the scientific international community has agreed upon a mutual objective, on a legal basis, to limit the increase of global temperature to maximum 2°C compared to the pre-industrial time (Vandyck et al., 2016 cited in Cai et al., 2018; Mutlu, Cindoruk, Y.O. and Cindoruk, S.S., 2020). In order to achieve this desideratum, it is mandatory that the global GHG emissions

to be reduced with 70% until 2050 (FAO, 2016 cited in Cai et al., 2018). Greenhouse gases are defined as: „atmospheric gases that absorb and re-emit long-wave radiation released by the earth back to the surface...” (Kebreab et al., 2006, p.136).

The main GHG include: methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrous oxide (N₂O), the radiation effects caused by them representing 80% out of the total emitted by all GHG (HFCs, PFCs, SF₆, NF₃, SF₅CF₃, H₂O (gaz), O₃) (Zhang et al., 2020).

The GHG emissions are quantified in **CO₂-eqv (Global Warming Potential)** for a period of time of 100 years, calculated in kg CO₂-eqv; taking in consideration the global warming potential for CO₂ (1), N₂O (298) and CH₄ (25) (Hagemann et al., 2011).

Nowadays, the higher and higher concentrations of greenhouse gases, especially methane and nitrous oxide, are raising critical environmental impacts, the main cause being their implications in the contemporary phenomenon of climate change (Ngwabie et al., 2018). Starting from this assumption, the specific professional literature investigates and highlights the fact that there is a connection between the livestock sector (bovine, pigs, ovine and poultry husbandry) (MADR Report, Project: ADER 9.1.4, Phase 1) and the anthropogenic GHG emissions (Hagemann et al., 2011); Phillipe and Nicks (2014) indicating that this sector is responsible, worldwide, for 18% of the total cumulated anthropogenic emissions, the percent of CO₂ being 9%, CH₄ between 35–40% and N₂O 65% (Battaglini et al., 2014).

Indubitably, animal husbandry sector is a major emitter of GHG, the generation taking place not only by direct emission, respectively through respiration, enteric fermentation, manure and gas exchange with the soil (Kebreab et al., 2006 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014), as well as through indirect emission from feed and forage production (inputs of fertilizers, pesticides and energy consumption related to production processes) and last but not least from the transport of animal products in various forms (fresh, refrigerated, frozen etc.) (Battaglini et al., 2014; Steinfeld et al., 2006).

The paper brings to the fore the livestock sector and its contribution as a major source of GHG, as described by the international scientific literature, proposing at the same time attenuation and mitigation methods of environmental impact for short, medium and long term, fundamental aspects if we take into consideration the ascendent global trend in respect of animal products consumption, especially meat.

METHODOLOGY

In order to shape this paper, from methodologically point of view, it was appealed to the identification of specific information regarding the approached research topic. To achieve this enterprise, bibliographic references were consulted (original articles, review articles, short communications, editorials) with the aid of Web of Science Clarivate Analytics. The main keywords used for the search were: „Greenhouse gas*” AND „Animal husbandry” OR „Livestock sector*”. The interrogation’s results generated 1139 responses, for the period 1977–2021, with the mention that the most were for the year 2020 (151 responses). From the total of 1139, a selection was made based on title and abstract, followed by the summarizing of the most representative for the research topic, in order to relieve the connection between animal husbandry sector and GHG emissions, with emphasis on applied methods, technologies and practices, having the aim to reduce the negative effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Animal husbandry must be regarded as one of the major sources of GHG emissions from agriculture when it comes to radiation potential and ozone layer depletion (Clemens and Ahlgrimm, 2001; Nguyen et al., 2013).

Livestock sector has witnessed a significant development over the last decades so it can respond to the increased needs of population in terms of meat consumption (Van der Heyden, Demeyer and Volcke, 2015) and it will continue to grow according to the estimations made until 2050 (see Table 1).

Table 1. Global meat consumption (in milion tons) (Phillipe and Nicks, 2014)

	2010	2020	2030	2050	Growth 2010-2050
Population (billion persons)	6.91	7.67	8.31	9.15	+32%
Meat consumption (million tons)					
Pig meat	102.3 (38%)	115.3 (36%)	129.9 (34%)	140.7 (30%)	+38%
Poultry meat	85.9 (32%)	111.0 (35%)	143.5 (38%)	193.3 (42%)	+125%
Bovine meat	67.3 (25%)	77.3 (24%)	88.9 (23%)	106.3 (23%)	+58%
Sheep/goat meat	13.2 (5%)	15.7 (5%)	18.5 (5%)	23.5 (5%)	+78%
All types of meat	268.7 (100%)	319.3 (100%)	380.8 (100%)	463.8 (100%)	+73%

Currently, worldwide, pork is the most consumed one, transforming in this way the sector of pig production in the second largest GHG emissions generator, the contribution percent being about 13%, the first place going to the bovine sector, with about 70% emissions (see Table 2) (Phillipe and Nicks, 2014). The contribution, broken down by main categories of animals, to the global quantities of greenhouse gases is (taking into account the global warming potential of 25 for CH₄ and 298 for N₂O (Phillipe and Nicks, 2014; MADR Report, Project: ADER 9.1.4, Phase 1) (see Table 2).

Table 2. Contribution of animal species to global emissions of GHG (Phillipe and Nicks, 2014)

GHG (milion tons CO ₂ equivalent year ¹)	CO ₂ emissions	CH ₄ emissions	N ₂ O emissions	Total emissions
Bovine/cattle	1,166.2 (61%)	2,072.8 (81%)	661.6 (60%)	3,900.6 (70%)
Small ruminants	69.9 (4%)	244.5 (10%)	202.6 (18%)	517 (9%)
Pigs	338.9 (18%)	237.3 (9%)	131.1 (12%)	707.3 (13%)
Poultry	332.2 (17%)	-	107.3 (10%)	439.5 (8%)
TOTAL	1,907.2 (100%)	2,554.5 (100%)	1,102.6 (100%)	5,564.3 (100%)

Analysing the aforementioned data, it can be easily observed that the main animal category responsible for the biggest percentages of GHG emissions is represented by bovine, respectively 81% CH₄, 61% CO₂ and 60% N₂O.

With a relative global warming potential of 25 (Seijan et al., 2011), **methane** is the main component out of the total GHG emissions produced by ruminants, 87% resulting from the microbial anaerobic fermentation in the rumen, 13% being attributed to the intestine (Battaglini et al., 2014). Enteric methane is produced in the ruminants' digestive tract by Archaea microorganisms, being a secondary product of anaerobic fermentation (methanogenesis) (Bell et al., 2014).

Martin, Morgavi and Doreau (2010) are indicating that ruminant animals release nearly 5% from the ingested digestible carbon in the form of CH₄. However, the emissions are believed to vary dependent on many parameters, such as: animal characteristics (breed, age, weight, physiological stage, production), nutritional plan or diet (intake, composition, digestibility), housing conditions, manure management (Hagemann et al., 2011; Battaglini et al., 2014; Philippe and Nicks, 2014; Bell et al., 2014; Beccaccia et al., 2015; Van der Heyden, Demeyer and Volcke, 2015; MADR Report, Project: ADER 9.1.4, Phase 1).

In the case of emissions resulted from manure management, they vary as a function of the manure quantity, its carbon and nitrogen content, temperature, anaerobic fermentations, type and time of storage (Battaglini et al., 2014). Ordinarily, the liquid manure storage systems are producing more CH₄ and the solid ones more N₂O (Amon et al., 2006; Sommer et al., 2009 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014). Other researches highlight the fact that in mountain areas, where the animal husbandry systems are relying mainly on grasslands and grazing, the quantities of methane are possibly higher because they are correlated with fiber digestion that takes place in the rumen (Clark, Kellihe and Pinares-Patino, 2011; Ramin and Huhtanen, 2013; Battaglini et al., 2014).

Nitrous oxide is produced as a result of „the nitrification of ammonium to nitrate or the incomplete denitrification of nitrate and is the main GHG emission derived from manure” (Battaglini et al., 2014, p.435). The N₂O emissions also depend on several factors, respectively: the manure quantity and its storage, soil and meteorological conditions, diets (Soussana et al., 2004; Gill, Smith and Wilkinson, 2010 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014). N₂O quantities tend to be larger when the available nitrogen exceeds the plant needs, especially when humidity levels are high (Smith and Conen, 2004; Luo et al., 2010 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014). Beside the previously mentioned, researchers refer also to indirect sources of N₂O emissions from agriculture, such as: volatilization of manure applied to soil, fertilizers containing nitrogen, loss of N that takes place as consequences of leachate and runoff processes (Battaglini et al., 2014). Like in the case of methane, the amounts of nitrous oxide tend to be higher in the animal husbandry systems which rely on grasslands and grazing, fact caused by the elimination and accumulation of animal feces into the ground and the anaerobic conditions created as a result of soil compaction through repeated animal trampling actions (van Groenigen et al., 2005; Hyde et al., 2006; Bhandral et al., 2010 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014). This circumstance is amplified by the soil humidity levels shortly after grazing (Saggar et al., 2004; van Beek et al., 2010 cited in Battaglini et al., 2014).

Dioxide carbon emissions resulted from the livestock sector are inferior to the methane and nitrous oxide ones (Battaglini et al., 2014). CO₂ results from the respiration and rumen anaerobic fermentation, but the largest amounts are related to the production of fertilizers and concentrates, electricity and the use of diesel fuels on the farm site (Steinfeld et al., 2006; Yan, Humphreys and Holden, 2013, Battaglini et al., 2014). Moreover, when the land is overgrazed, the combination between vegetation loss and soil trampling can lead to the

carbon loss from soil and release of CO₂ (Abril, Barttfeld and Bucher, 2005; Steinfeld et al., 2006; Battaglini et al., 2014). It should also be noted that in forage-based livestock production and rearing systems, the carbon sequestration and storage capacity of grasslands is extremely important (Battaglini et al., 2014).

In view of these aspects, the scientific literature indicates a number of formulas and equations having the aim to facilitate the calculation of CH₄ și CO₂ emissions at farm level. Therefore, Philippe and Nicks (2014) suggest the following equation (1) in order to estimate the exhaled CO₂ (E-CO₂, pig, in kg CO₂ day⁻¹) for pigs with a body weight (BW) between 20–120 kg:

$$E - CO_2, pig = 0.136 BW^{0.573} \quad (1)$$

Making the calculation, it results that the produced exhaled CO₂, for a pig with a body weight of 70 kg would be of **1.55 kg day⁻¹** (Philippe and Nicks, 2014), the authors concluding that the exhaled emissions of CO₂ depend of body weight, physiological age, production level and nutritional input of animal. Regarding the CH₄, the same authors (Philippe and Nicks, 2014), propose equations (2) (3) useful to determine the enteric CH₄ (E-CH₄, pig/sow, in g CH₄ day⁻¹) resulted from the digestible fibres (dRes g day⁻¹) for fattening pigs and adult sows:

$$E - CO_4, pig = 0.012 \times dRes \quad (2)$$

$$E - CO_4, sow = 0.021 \times dRes \quad (3)$$

In order to determine CH₄ released from manure (E-CH₄, manure, in m³) one must consider the quantity of excreted solid volatile (VS) or organic matter (OM), in kg, the final potential of CH₄ (B₀), in m³ CH₄/ kg VS or OM and the conversion factor of methane (MCF), in percent (Philippe and Nicks, 2014) (4):

$$E - CH_4, bălegar = VS \times B_0 \times MCF \quad (4)$$

It is recommended that the values for VS, B₀ and MCF to be distinct in terms of regions of the world, climate, animal categories and manure type (Philippe and Nicks, 2014).

For N₂O calculation (which results only from manure, taking into consideration only pig farms) it is suggested to multiply the N excreted by the animals (N_{ex}) with a specific conversion factor attributed to each type of manure management (Philippe and Nicks, 2014).

For a correct quantification of eructed CH₄ emissions by cows from commercial farms, Bell et al. (2014) appealed to the formula (5):

$$CH_4 (mg/l) = \text{average integral of } CH_4/\text{eructation} \times \text{frequency of eructations} \times \text{dilution factor} \quad (5)$$

It's worth noting that the methane emissions were measured during milking, for seven days in a row, animals being fed with concentrated forages, in small quantities, during the whole milking process. Inside the feed bins were placed CH₄ analysers which captured and measured the released CH₄ through eructation and respiration.

Summarizing the results indicated by the researchers in terms of quantifying CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions and the factors that influence them we can conclude the following: the emissions are associated and largely depend on the type of diet/feed (fiber content, crude protein), age, body weight, physiological state, production level, animal housing conditions, manure management. Some examples from international researches and their conclusions, presented brief and concise, include:

- In case of pigs, the alteration of protein source led to significant changes of urine and faeces content, of crude protein digestibility and of carbohydrates fraction modification. The CH₄ emission potential was higher in the case of soy diets and lower in the sunflower ones (Beccaccia et al., 2015);
- The fattening period contributes with a higher than 70% percent out of total emissions, gestation, lactation and weaning periods contributing each with approximately 10% (Philippe and Nicks, 2014);
- The dry matter input, respectively the diet composition contribute mainly to enteric methane production in case of milk cows (Bell and Eckard, 2012; Bell et al., 2014);
- Important effects on emissions have had the lactation week (emissions have grown in the first 20 weeks, remained relatively constant between week 21–50; varying from 2.2 mg/l to 3.2mg/l (week 50) (Bell et al., 2014);
- Emissions were positively correlated with dry matter consuming and negatively with concentrates proportion from diet (Bell et al., 2014);
- Emissions have increased along with milk production growth, highlighting the positive relation between this and dry matter consumption (Bell et al., 2014);
- The methane release rate is higher during milking than in the rest of the day (Bell et al., 2014);
- GHG emissions at farm level are around 80–307 kg CO₂-eqv/100/kg energy corrected milk (ECM), having a lower value in developed countries and a higher one in developing countries (Hagemann et al., 2011);
- GHG emissions at farm gate are lower for big farms with higher productivity than for small farms from developing countries (there were studied 45 farms from 38 countries), the emissions average being 135 kg CO₂-eqv/100 kg energy corrected milk (ECM) (Hagemann et al., 2011);
- The manure management type has a big influence on GHG emissions, so that its frequent disposal contributes to the decrease of CH₄, CO₂, N₂O; the combination of disposal operations with specific storage conditions and appropriate treatment being also beneficial (Philippe and Nicks, 2014);
- In general, the adoption of a proper farm management will implicitly lead to maintaining an optimal level of GHG emissions (Philippe and Nicks, 2014).

Given the current situation of the main GHG emissions from the livestock sector and the fact that it has intensified globally in recent decades, various methods for mitigation them are required.

Clemens and Ahlgrimm (2001) mention in their study two types of methods for reducing greenhouse gas emissions resulting from livestock sector, respectively animal husbandry, namely: preventive and end pipe. Generally, reduction methods target direct GHG emissions (resulting from the digestive and metabolic processes of animals, as well as from excretion processes) and to a lesser extent the indirect ones (fertilizer production, transport) (Clemens and Ahlgrimm, 2001). Therefore, CH₄ resulting from digestive processes and nitrogen gaseous compounds from feces can be controlled by manipulating the diet, respectively optimizing it (Clemens and Ahlgrimm, 2001).

Gill, Smith and Wilkinson (2010) point out that better management of grasslands and manure, improving the efficiency of animal production through superior reproduction, health interventions or improving fertility can have a direct impact on reducing GHG emissions.

Martin, Morgavi and Doreau (2010) indicate that reducing GHG emissions from ruminants, enteric CH₄ in this case, without altering animal production, is a purpose both to mitigate emissions and to improve feed conversion efficiency. Thus, they claim that reducing CH₄ emissions in ruminants is possible by adopting various strategies, feed management being the most convenient method because it is the most developed. Other methods, which include biotechnologies, the use of additives, sound promising, but the diversity and plasticity of functions of bacterial and methanogenic communities present the rumen may be a limiting factor for their successful application (Martin, Morgavi and Doreau, 2010). Despite this, it is worth mentioning a few: controlling methanogenesis through vaccines or the use of bacteriocins, the use of probiotics (acetogens, live yeasts), the removal of protozoa from the rumen, the use of feed additives (ionophores, organic acids and plant extracts) (Martin, Morgavi and Doreau, 2010). Researches show that the potential use of plant extracts to reduce CH₄ is gaining ground, as these extracts are seen as a natural alternative to chemical additives, being well perceived by consumers (Martin, Morgavi and Doreau, 2010).

Nguyen et al. (2013) proposed the use of various agricultural practices and alternative land use to contribute to the short- and medium-term reduction of GHG from beef cattle production systems.

Because animal husbandry and production systems vary considerably from country to country, GHG mitigation strategies need to be adapted to the specific circumstances of each country (Sejian et al., 2011). Therefore, the research undertaken by Sejian et al. (2011) focused on identifying enteric CH₄ reduction strategies, which they grouped into three categories: management strategies, nutrition strategies and other strategies. The first category includes: extended lactation, reducing the number of animals, improved nutrition, strategic supplementation, enhancement agents to increase production, improved genetic selection, improved grassland management (Sejian et al., 2011). The second category includes: concentrates supplementation, dietary modification – NH₃, molasses, propionate enhancers, oil supplementation, ionophores supplementation – Monensin, defaunation, tannin supplementation (Sejian et al., 2011). The third category includes strategies related to immunization, recombinant technology, reducing livestock, reducing animal products, chemical inhibitors, microbial intervention in the rumen (Sejian et al., 2011).

It should be noted, however, that these new and advanced methods of mitigation are promising, but extensive research is still needed to validate these approaches and evaluate their *in vivo* effectiveness in reducing CH₄ emissions (Sejian et al., 2011).

Another effective method in reducing GHG is provided by the world's grasslands (native and cultivated), one of their important functions being to sequester carbon in the soil, this topic being addressed in numerous studies. The ability of grasslands to store carbon in the soil is estimated to be similar in order of magnitude to that of cultivated lands and forests, and is currently considered a key tool in the adoption of national GHG mitigation strategies in many countries around the world (Henderson et al., 2015). The research conducted by Henderson et al. (2015) involved different models (Century and Daycent) for calculating changes in soil carbon stocks, N₂O emissions from soil and forages generated by ruminants. The authors indicate three different practices whose ultimate goal is carbon sequestration through grasslands: improved grazing management, legume sowing, and nitrogen fertilization. According to their study, the annual net carbon sequestration potential was 295 Tg CO₂ yr⁻¹, which is much lower than the global estimates from other studies (Smith et al., 2007; Lal,

2004 cited in Henderson et al., 2015). However, it should be mentioned and insisted that the areas where the above-mentioned practices can be successfully applied to reach the mentioned potential should be identified a priori, as there is also the risk of increasing greenhouse gas emissions (especially in the case of legumes).

Sanz-Cobena et al. (2016) focused their concerns to mediterranean agroecosystems and investigated different management practices to reduce GHG (N_2O and CH_4) and sequester carbon. The authors indicated that the best GHG mitigation strategies would be:

- Adjusting the amount of nitrogen fertilizer according to crop requirements, both in the case of those connected to irrigation systems and in the case of those irrigated with rainwater (N_2O emissions can be reduced by up to 50% compared to not adjusting the amount of fertilizer);
- Replacing synthetic nitrogen fertilizers with manure can reduce N_2O emissions by 20% (in mediterranean climate conditions) bringing at the same time additional indirect benefits related to energy conservation and increasing crop yields;
- The use of urea and nitrification inhibitors increases the utilization rate of N in crops, thus reducing N_2O emissions by up to 80% and 50%, respectively;
- A percent between 3–15% of N_2O emissions can be reduced by diminishing food waste, a 40% reduction in meat and dairy consumption can cut emissions by 20–30%.

With a wide range of GHG mitigation strategies available, it is necessary to have an in-depth understanding of each individual's mode of action and to choose those that are financially efficient, improve productivity and have limited potential negative effects on animal production, paying attention to all GHG emissions from animal production systems.

CONCLUSIONS

There is no doubt that the livestock sector contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and that the demand for animal products is increasing, especially in developing countries where economic sectors are constantly growing. If we talk about GHG emissions broken down into animal categories, it is obvious that monogastric are more efficient than ruminants.

Actions that can be taken to reduce GHG emissions can be grouped into three categories, as indicated by Gill, Smith and Wilkinson (2010):

- **for the short-term (immediate):** the accelerated knowledge transfer towards improving the efficiency of animal production systems from researchers with preoccupations in the livestock sector and policy makers to producers and consumers, in order to facilitate the choice of the best methods to reduce emissions of GES;
- **for the medium term:** mandatory interdisciplinary collaboration for researchers working in the animal sector with researchers from other fields to gather knowledge about the economic, social and environmental consequences of livestock agriculture, in a way that can be understood and used by the political community, to support future decisions, not only on climate change, but also on food security;
- **for the long-term:** continuous investments in the development and implementation of new technologies that have the potential to reduce GHG emissions and radically change animal production systems.

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